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SERVING THE UNDERSERVED: A TEAM-BASED OUTREACH MODEL FOR DELIVERING HOME CARE IN A MARGINALISED COMMUNITY

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Introduction: Access to healthcare remains a significant challenge for individuals living in underserved and marginalised communities, such as urban slums. Social exclusion, poverty, and limited health literacy often contribute to poor health-seeking behaviours and interrupted care. In such contexts, effective healthcare delivery requires not only individual effort but coordinated action from the primary healthcare team.

Case presentation: Ms. AB, is a 62-year-old woman diagnosed with schizophrenia, on treatment for the past 20 years. She also receives ongoing care for diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and drug-induced parkinsonism, with scheduled follow-up at a divisional hospital medical clinic every two months. She resides in Maligawatta area with her only living relative — an unmarried sister who is also the principal caregiver, but lacks a stable income.

During routine clinic visits, the medical officer noted that the patient herself was absent, with her sister collecting medications on her behalf. Further inquiry revealed that the patient had become bedbound due to advanced parkinsonism and was unable to attend clinic appointments. Recognising the need for continuity of care, the head of the institution arranged community-based care delivery via the Public Health Nursing Officer (PHNO). She was accompanied by a healthcare assistant familiar with the area to ensure her personal safety during field visits.

Despite challenges in her social and environmental context, the patient continues to receive consistent home-based care, helping her maintain optimal control of chronic conditions. With support from the PHNO, her caregiver was trained in essential aspects of care. A trusting relationship with the healthcare team has sustained this patient-centred approach.

Conclusion: This case demonstrates a meaningful example of team-based, equity-driven, community care in a highly underserved setting and offers a practical model for delivering community-based care in marginalised settings.

Key words: community-based care, marginalised populations, multidisciplinary healthcare

